

The Value of Sound within a Multisensory Approach to AR in the Arts

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Abstract. We explore the potential of sound within broader multisensory augmented reality, and its value in creating coherent, immersive and embodied experiences in computational art. We demonstrate this practically through accounts of the authors experiences in creating two pieces. Looking at the wider place of AR in the arts, we argue that DIY approaches to augmented reality are essential for creative work, and we speculate on how art can contribute to future theory, technologies and practice in the field.

Keywords: augmented reality · multisensory experience · embodied experience · digital culture

1 Multisensory AR: arts and digital culture

This position paper introduces the authors’ ongoing practice research into augmented reality in the arts, within the Experimental Music Technologies lab at the University of Sussex, UK. Our broad approach is focused on the potential of sound in the multisensory mix, and draw from enactivist approaches to designing embodied systems. We conceptualise AR within our work as “real-time computationally mediated perception” [8].

The paper discusses the theoretical framework behind our approach, before introducing two AR artworks: Listening Mirrors (Chevalier & Kiefer), and area~ (Bilbow). These investigate sensory modalities afforded by AR technology to develop new understandings of embodied experiences located in digital culture.

In working within digital culture and the arts, we recognise two points of resistance that are reflected in consumer-level AR technology: the prioritisation of the visual over other senses, and of information delivery over immersive experience. To address these points, the artworks take a Do-It-Yourself (DIY) approach to multisensory system building that empowers the individual artist (or artist collective) by overcoming labor distribution and economic restrictions. Furthermore, a DIY approach offers unique creative freedoms that are discussed in section 4.

2 Multisensory AR: perception and agency

The enactivist principles describe how cognition is inseparable from and intertwined with the environment. They specify that cognition is embodied, embed-

ded, enacted, and extended [13]. We draw from these principles to provide a framework in which to think about the design of augmented reality experiences. The ‘4Es’ can be considered as conditions for what we might describe as immersive, rich experience. In previous work, enactivist principles have been offered as guidelines for the creation of interactive systems; both Essl and O’Modhrain [12] and Armstrong [1] suggest this approach in the design of new musical instruments. Our approach extends this work towards augmented reality systems; we now explore in more detail how the ‘4Es’ apply in our work.

2.1 Embodied AR

To provide immersive and embodied experiences of computationally mediated environments and processes, AR must engage our bodies; as we humans experience the world in a multisensory fashion, so too must the technology that we hope will provide us with embodied experience be able to engage our multiple senses.

As artists interested in experimental music technologies, the medium we engage in driving these experiences is sound. To be clear, by taking a sound-driven perspective towards multisensory AR, we are not arguing against visual-driven approaches to multisensory AR, instead we seek to dismantle and create new hierarchies of sensory engagement, aiming to develop novel sonic experiences.

The sonic potential of AR was realised as early as 1993 by Cohen et al [9], in their work utilising HRTF research in the field of telepresence. This was only shortly after AR’s original definition by Caudell and Mizell [6]; and although Azuma’s following survey from 1997 conceptualises AR as having a multisensory potential [3], a survey conducted in 2018 found that 96% of AR usability studies conducted from 2005-2014 augmented the visual sense [11]. This tendency towards visual AR demonstrates an ocular-centrism that has led to non-visual senses being considered as afterthoughts to AR experiences rather than being designed for holistically.

The three typical forms of AR that Azuma et al. [2] recognise: head-mounted, handheld, and projection AR are now very mature technologies, but despite this have only very recently been explored in terms of sonic and multisensory approaches. The Microsoft HoloLens 2, using Mixed Reality Tool Kit, has access to binaural spatial audio. The Magic Leap ML-1 offers similar HTRF-based spatial audio rendering. Within commercial-level hand-held AR use, audio is too, only just emerging as design possibility with specific SDKs in Google’s ARCore and Apple’s ARKit enabling positional audio. In the last year specifically, ARKit has access to head-tracked 6DoF if the user is wearing Apple AirPods Pros, broadening the possibilities for sound-driven handheld AR experiences. Projection AR has seen the least development in terms of sound-driven AR experiences, despite there being a rich history of situated spatial audio in the arts. We recognise the latent possibilities of technologies such as wavefield synthesis [17] and ambisonic beam-forming in delivering large-scale and projected sound-driven AR experiences. We therefore argue an embodied experience in AR is necessarily and by definition, multisensory.

2.2 Embedded AR

From this position of multisensory embodiment, we also come to acknowledge that various processes or “relationships” within AR are embedded within the specificity of the devices and environments that enable these experiences. Often, it is remarked that the experience afforded by AR is “context-aware”; these devices are reprocessing data about our environment in real-time and offer “relevant” information that is layered on top of those data.

Schraffenberger defines these processes as “content based” and “spatial” relationships respectively, between the “real and virtual” [19, p. 80, 84]. Typical consumer AR experiences today often fulfil both of these descriptions, for example, GPS navigation delivered through a visual AR display; point-of-interest (POI) information overlay through a hand-held smartphone. Two further relationship types are defined by Schraffenberger: “physical”, which describes experiences in which there is dynamic interaction and affect between real and virtual processes, and “behavioural”, in which the real and virtual “sense and react to each other” [19, p. 116, 121].

Our own position posits that the potential of AR is to provide much richer and immersive sonic experiences of “real and virtual” than just informational layering, and align ourselves with creating effects through our own work similar to those described in Schraffenberger’s “physical” and “behavioural” conceptions. An important question for us as artists therefore, is what the nature of these relationships are that are embedded in our environment, and what do they teach us about our own, broader digital culture?

2.3 Enacted AR

An enactive approach to AR implies that the experience of an AR environment arises from the participants interactions with the world. A useful distinction is Armstrong’s separation of functional and realisational interfaces [1, p. 41]. A functional interface offers linear paths of interactivity, while a realisational interface offers an emergent dialogue, and deep embodied intertwining, between participant and environment. We see live environmental sound processing as a valuable method for achieving this complex coupling. Audio processing offers the potential for perceptually realistic modulation of the sonic environment, where simple transformations can radically change how the body couples with the world.

Within contemporary art practice, pioneers such as the Manifest.AR group were able to create convincing and socially immersive AR art using only visual layering¹. They did this through aligning the enacted nature of AR with political expression. By creating an app that overlaid visual art (content-based) within the Museum of Modern Art (MoMA) through GPS (spatial), they allowed participants to visit an exhibition in the museum that had not been organised by

¹ <http://www.sndrv.nl/moma/>

MoMA themselves. AR thereby afforded these artists the ability to embed virtual art within an area considered private property, and also promote collective AR agency, raising very early questions about “virtual trespass” with AR.

2.4 Extended AR

Designing for multisensory AR acknowledges that its processes (typically augmentation) have the potential for our cognition to be extended into our environment and facilitate networked expression with the environment and other actors within it. Our position is that AR provides the opportunity to not only augment, i.e. add to reality, but to mediate our perception of the real world, i.e. diminish, transform, enhance, enrich. Although this thinking has existed since close to the conception of AR [16] [2], current consumer and enterprise level AR still lacks the ability to do much other than *add* layers of graphical (and sometimes auditory) information on top of our real environment in three dimensions.

Considerable research has been conducted so far concerning the technical challenges involving (visual) augmentation, i.e. occlusion, alignment of virtual objects (registration), and brightness. In our work we try to focus on how these challenges and new ones extend to atypical (non-augmenting) AR processes. Schraffenberger defines these as “subforms” of AR, and includes among them: extended, hybrid, diminished and altered reality, as well as extended perception [19, pp. 89-115].

Within our own creative practice, it is our experience that different interaction paradigms and behaviours emerge dependent on the process elected. Especially within installations, it is a key research question of ours that asks: in what ways can we facilitate expressive interactions between participants? What modes of interaction and “conversation” between participants and environment arise from processes that, for example, *replace* specific environmental sounds with virtual ones; that *modulate* real voices with virtual ones?

3 Listening Mirrors

Listening Mirrors² (Chevalier & Kiefer) is an augmented reality art installation, that creates a shared augmented environment between multiple participants. This environment is hybrid, comprising an physically altered acoustic environment (using an acoustic mirror), and a computationally altered environment that participants experience through a wearable audio AR device, the Audiomented Sound System.

Sound in Listening Mirrors is the primary driver of our multisensory approach, but also draws in haptics and proprioception. We explore the cross-modal potential of augmented sound to disrupt the participants’ senses of space, touch, and self.

Participants in Listening Mirrors wear our networked AR device, with bone conduction headphones so that we can merge computer-generated sound with

² <http://listeningmirrors.net/>

Fig. 1. Listening Mirrors

natural hearing. A microphone records their breath and vocalisations, and processes it such that they are given a heightened awareness of their own body. The participant also hears the sound from other participants' vocalisations, creating a shared sound world and a shared embodied experience. This shared sound world can be heard and felt through the resonant acoustic mirror. Participants are invited to explore the sounds it can make; these sounds are processed and merged into the AR world. This combination of acoustic and computational sound generation and listening creates a shared sonic world that challenges existing socially/culturally conditioned sound hierarchies and invites the exploration and creation of multiple sensory bodies with AR and networked technology, leading us to explore multi-sensory and collective experiences.

The motivations for, technical details about and participant evaluations of Listening Mirrors are described in more detail in [14,7]

4 area~ and polaris~

area~³ (Billow) is a augmented reality instrument that enables users to record, manipulate and spatialise virtual audio samples or *nodes* around their immediate environment using hand-gesture and head-movement. It was developed as a prototype exploration into the effectiveness of non-visual augmented reality processes in providing new aesthetic sonic experiences.

Adopting a maker/DIY approach to designing an interactive AR system was invaluable for several reasons. Firstly, it enabled quick customisation of parameter values, gestures, and auditory effects, specifically through the use of a visual programming language (Max MSP). Secondly, it means that the system can be

³ https://sambilbow.com/projects/2020_05area/

Fig. 2. area~

Fig. 3. polaris~

customised in the future to suit new, perhaps larger environments with multiple participants with relative ease. Thirdly, the cost of the system was very low due to the use of off-the-shelf and DIY electronics components, for which wide a community of makers creating with similar components often contribute in troubleshooting issues.

There are three input modalities for area~, an ambisonic microphone, which allows the location specific recording of sounds in three-dimensions (although the currently, area~ operates only in the horizontal plane); a Leap Motion infrared camera system, which affords high precision hand-tracking; and an inertial measurement unit (IMU) affixed to the side of the head-worn component of the system, which aids in rendering head orientation dependent real-time binaural audio. Playing area~ is a three stage process, recording, manipulating, spatialising. For a full explanation and description of the audio effects and their gesture mappings, see [5]. This process can be repeated up to eight times, to create a richly mediated sonic environment that blends the virtual *nodes* into the performer’s auditory environment. The output of the AR processes is via bone conduction headphones, a popular method of AR auditory display due to their unobtrusive design not occluding users’ hearing of the real world [15].

This prototype interactive AR system was developed through an autobiographical design method [10]. Through this approach, experiences of use have been documented, notably, the ability to (1) gesturally blend real and virtual sound environments into a hybrid environment (2) manipulate through responsive real-time audio effects, the perception of this hybrid environment and (3) create believable sensory illusions of real-world sound sources from these *nodes*. Integrating other senses is the next stage of the creative process for this prototype system, after which it will be named polaris~. In order to integrate the visual sense, the open-source and 3D printable Project North Star AR headset⁴ will be used. Its open-source nature provides the freedom to integrate further senses, and further writing on these developments can be found in [4]. Figure 3 shows the headset in use with the default Microsoft Mixed Reality Tool Kit virtual piano, through the community developed Project Esky framework [18].

⁴ <https://docs.projectnorthstar.org/>

5 Reflections

We can see the ‘4Es’ of (radical) enactivism as conditions for creating rich multisensory AR experiences, which in-turn offer the opportunity to explore broader aspects of augmented experience: sensory hierarchies, collective experience, creative expression, shared perception, biofeedback through modulation of self-perception. These themes are present in the two pieces described here, which create augmented experience through changing the way in which participants couple with the environment through altering sound perception.

From our experience of creating these AR pieces, we see the value of sound in the wider multisensory mix as follows: (1) sound can create perceptually realistic immersive and seamless experiences: realtime processing of environment sound can create profound changes in how participants intertwine with their environment (as reported by participants) (2) sound bridges the senses, and can create cross-modal effects, for example augmented sound can change perception of touch, and can alter our perception of space (3) sound can redirect our awareness and reprioritise our perception of the world. Putting these together in the form of AR installation environments gives the artist wide flexibility in creating novel experiences and narratives.

We recognise that our alignment with the ‘4Es’ of (radical) enactivism is not exhaustive of our position and approach, and acknowledge that working with new perceptions and agencies of people and spaces requires nuanced discussion. In particular, future work will aim to devise a framework that introduces concepts such as new materialism to tackle social, political, and economic hierarchies inherent to dealing with AR in the arts, moreover, addressing the visual bias and lack of multisensory approaches to consumer AR systems.

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